

TAI TIORI TAI PARI

Ko te tai he kupu whakarite mō te pikinga tahi me te noho tahi.

He whakaatūranga rōpū nā ngā kaitoi me ngā kaihoahoa mai i Toi Ohomai Te Pūkenga e whakaatu ana ki te whakahē i te tai hou mai o Te Awanui, e pā ana ki te wāhi o te Papa Unaunahi.

Ka tuhurahia te huringa, te kotahitanga me te tika mā te whakamahi i ngā hangarau tuku iho me ngā hangarau matihiko e korero ana ki o tātou iwi mō te wā me te wāhi, e mihi ana me te mohio ki o tātou hitori me te hiahia mō te whakahoahoa.

The tide is a metaphor for how we rise together and reside together.

A group exhibition by local artists and designers from Toi Ohomai Te Pūkenga is set visibly against the incoming and outgoing tide of Te Awanui, echoing the location of the Papa Unaunahi (Cargo Shed).

Change, unity and equity is explored using traditional and digital technologies that speak to our people about time and place, acknowledging and understanding our history and desire for partnership.

No. <edition number>/200

19th - 23rd October, 2023
Tauranga Arts Festival
Papa Unaunahi (The Cargo Shed)

Participating artists

Darcell Apelu
Karolina Bemova
Quinton Bidois
Riley Claxton
Donna Dinsdale
Heidi Douglas
Nicol Sanders-OShea
Dale Sattler [illustration, catalogue]
Kyle Sattler
Anne-Marie Simon

Essay

Nicol Sanders-OShea

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Tai Timu Tai Pari: The Ebb and Flow of Changemakers

The collective of artists in this exhibition have a strong sense of belonging and hail to Tauranga Moana or the wider Bay of Plenty. Some of the artists were born and raised in this part of the motu (island), others have found their way seeking opportunities, future possibilities and whanau (family). We developed a theme that draws upon the location of the exhibition site, the Cargo Shed at the edge of Taumata Kahawai. Tai Timu Tai Pari was agreed as the expression of the notions of change, unity, equity and movement which became the driver of their creative ideas.

The Cargo Shed is located in Tauranga's history of confiscation and contest for occupation and authority rights. The Te Papa Peninsula is long overdue for reconciliation to heal relationships with mana whenua, to apologise, acknowledge and amend past actions towards a future that is inclusive, prosperous and united. The exhibition aligns with Tauranga City Council's 2022 strategic document, Te Rapunga Ora ki Te Papa, outlining the Council's investment plan and vision.

"...mana whenua restoring their mana rangatiranga over the city centre, through protecting, enhancing, commemorating and celebrating those areas of significance to mana whenua. In doing so, it also aims to enrich the culture and identity for the wider community and future generations to come".

Individually, the creative thinking process has generated a range of visual, audio and kinaesthetic responses among the exhibiting artists. Movement is dominant in and surrounding the newly renovated space; the water of Te Awanui is calming and visually

audible, the sound of the waves is seen not heard. **Kyle Sattler's** video stills from crude wave props made from cardboard initially promoted the context of this exhibition in the Tauranga Arts Festival programming information. The wave motif was extracted from a stop-motion animated music video for the song 'Bing Bong Dong' produced by 'We Will Ride Fast'. Through a process of manipulation, the moving image sequences were created to form a collection of ripples. Presented as a multi-monitor video installation of memorising flat rippling waves next to the windows link intentionally to the waves outside. Sound is embedded into each monitor output to stimulate an experience of synchysis, when audio and visual phenomenon occurs at the same time. Audio and visual dualities occur simultaneously such as Authenticity and Replication; Location and Dislocation; Together and Apart; Freedom and Conformity.

In **Darcell Apelu's** floor installation, pools of reflective text directly reference wai (water) as attributes to change and its persistent presence. For Māori, wai is understood to have the function of imbuing mauri (life force) and mana (authority, prestige, guiding values). It is how and when water is needed that makes it sacred, from our birth through to our death. Te Ao Māori is explored, imbuing a sense of well-being in our physical, spiritual, emotional, communal and environmental existence. In her recent sculpture 'Death of Prosperity', water runs down a series of translucent chairs, signifying whakapapa, genealogy lineage and the idea of 'trickle-down' economics of heritage. The text additions provoke the viewer to consider their position in the world, asking 'Does the mindset need to change? And if not why not?'. Darcell's work 'You Leave Traces in

My Blood' considers the impact of environment, the spaces that are occupied and how a Māori worldview and Eurocentric position can work in partnership with one another. The text considers us all to be whenua (land) while simultaneously being wai, a moving body of water leaving an impact, impression or trace on one another.

Dale Sattler's illustrations 'Flood', 'High', 'Ebb' and 'Low' capture four stages of tidal movement, which he explains as a personal reflection of his relationship and journey with his youngest child and their time together going from Sulphur Point to the Strand Reserve playground. These outings reflect the emotional and physical experiences of rising and falling. Like tides, his child starts off excited and full of energy, in hope of seeing taraka (truck), tereina (train), aki aki (beating), pahi (winning) and other youthful delights. Then eventually to the journey home again, tired and grumpy, yearning to be with mum and a bottle of tasty liquid. 'Tai Timu Tai Pari' thematically resonates with Dale's parental expectations and the future relationship with his child, rising together with successes and learning from failures. These illustrations play with typographic legibility; fragmented textual narrative design elements derived from conversations with his child while on their journey. For Dale, a sense of place is iterative; relationships with sites come and go like the ebb and flow of the tide. He questions whether the inherent aspects of the site shape a sense of place, and how to consider the legacy of the past responsibly. He considers the weight of our land's history and if a contemporary perspective can influence the future, when a record of a personal relationship between father and son seems so important in the present.

Nicol Sanders-O'Shea's print installation reveals a physically demanding process, a creative journey that is unique, repetitive and endless. For Nicol it is a creative search for meaning in a period of constant change. Framed designs stylistically mimic waves that project shadows onto the wall around each work creating a sense of rising and falling, depth and height. The process of printing, the choice of colour, the construction and the installation en masse, celebrate change and her own challenge of endurance and resilience as a mother, artist and manager of

people. Māori values of waiora, taiora, te oranga and ngā manukura resonate strongly with her; associated to the physical environment, the people in her care, the education and well-being of herself and others are important aspects motivating, building and nurturing relationships that are collaborative and inclusive. Individual works are presented together as a group, perhaps a metaphor for being together in changing times, and how water connects people and culture.

Anne-Marie Simon takes inspiration from the ever-changing nature of the ocean and the curious creatures that exist below. Finding profound meaning in the ethereal grace of jellyfish, their sense of freedom and autonomy. Creating thread versions using an unconventional creative approach employing a domestic sewing machine and dissolvable fabric, carefully crafting three-dimensional thread sculptures to be hung in space. Like a fish out of water, these works are viewed up high, away from water, with no desire to return. The core Māori concepts of Tino Rangatiratanga and Mana Motuhake have overlapping meaning related to the possibility to live with sovereignty, autonomy, independence, self-governance and self-determination. In considering these concepts, Anne-Marie's work shows us the potential for change might seem disconnected from our current environment, but could bring koha (gifts) beyond what we know now. Ko ngā pae tawhiti, whāia kia tata. Ko ngā pae tata, whakamaua kia tina. The potential for tomorrow depends on what we do today.

Riley Claxton is influenced by 19th century maps and the stylised drawing of water. Exploring this historic style of drawing in the form of large containers as vessels for water. One depicts an image of a woman's profile to celebrate the beauty of water and reference water in the creation and significance in sustaining life. Another is an image of a bomb. A double meaning is created to question if this work is a ticking time bomb referencing climate change or simply a water bomb to be played with? In the photographic series he investigates the changing states of water within the Bay of Plenty region. His images capture the contrast between the natural geothermal activity against the urban/suburban lifestyle, entertainment and tourist attractions

unique to Rotorua/Waiariki where he lives. Indeed, 'Waiariki' refers to the healing waters in this area. Wairere waterfall is located at the Buried Village just outside of Rotorua on the way to Lake Tarawera. It is where the emerald green water from Lake Rotokakahi, known by locals as the 'Green Lake', flows through onto Lake Tarawera. The waterfall is a reminder of the purity and journey of water as something constantly changing and moving. This series was recently exhibited in Rotorua titled 'Spend a night not a fortune', to question the illusion of tourism, but when exhibiting the same work at the Cargo Shed, these photos instead form an exchange between Rotorua and Tauranga, referring to the history of trade in the Bay of Plenty.

Ko wai mātou translates to both 'we are water' and 'who we are', as water is considered central to a sense of identity and well-being. **Karolina Bemova** explores new technologies to better understand her identity. Her role at Toi Ohomai Te Pūkenga is to support student learning across a range of creative digital technologies, she is equally invested in her own learning as it has purpose for herself and others. Karolina investigates 3D printing and laser cut slicing methods demonstrating her expertise while appreciating her ancestry and cultural foundations that form her sense of identity. The decorative motif, reminiscent of patterns across Europe, are nostalgic for her. New creative research into Identity through technology can be transformative in their impact on the sustainability of culture. Karolina presents a modified animal skull with digitally created versions to question whether technology can authentically preserve the skills and knowledge inherited from ancestry.

Identity and fashion are considered intrinsically connected, in which clothing is clearly a declaration or a manifestation of identity. Clothing can serve as a visible and powerful statement, it can convey messages about status, values and cultural heritage. **Donna Dinsdale** identifies as Ngāti Pākehā, through marriage, she is part of a wider whānau Ngāti Marukukere, Hāpu of Tapuika Iwi, of Te Arawa Waka in the Bay of Plenty region. She is supported by her whānau to uphold the principles of Te Tiriti o Waitangi and Mātauranga Māori through collaboration, discussion and consultation, kawa

(cultural practices) and tikanga (cultural principles). Understanding how aspects of a Māori worldview can be embedded into practice in a respectful manner has become an integral component of her research and growth as an educator and creative practitioner. For Donna, fashion serves as a reflection of, and a catalyst for change, renewal, equity and movement within the cultural and historical context of Aotearoa. The work is thoughtful and historically loaded. The period prior to 1838 and the Treaty signing is a significant time in our history, and Donna chooses to reference women's apparel of this period as a way to anchor the work in a specific time and place. By drawing upon this historical context Donna refers to how broader societal forces shape fashion and identity. Her work engages the viewer in a critical examination of the past and present, using clothing as a lens through which to understand and potentially reshape societal dynamics.

Heidi Douglas moved to New Zealand from California in 2004, choosing to live alongside Mauao (Mount Maunganui) as her place in the world to raise her children. Her photography represents a deepening relationship with whenua as a first-generation immigrant. As tauiwi (non-Indigenous to Aotearoa), she acknowledges the decolonising process, requiring a changing mindset in order to adapt to her adopted homeland. Using the lens as a witnessing device, Heidi examines her relationship with her mountain 'Ko Mauao te maunga'. Capturing change events on the maunga, to present the cyclical nature of life, restorative practice, destruction and ultimately, the knowledge and importance of valuing the whenua. The site of this exhibition is perched atop the ebbing flow of the tides of the bay. The same water and sea life come and go beneath the pilings, just as they swirl around Mauao and all of Te Moana-a-Toi (Bay of Plenty). These photos signal our land and with it, the beauty, attention and respect it deserves as reflected in the Te Tiriti obligations. Heidi's photographic series is based on the principles of Kaitiakitanga, the guardianship and protection of our environment based on a Māori world view to present reciprocity, active protection, partnership, equity and equality.

Quinton Bidois (Ngāti Ranginui, Ngai Te Rangi) presents a perspex box, although it is not merely a

box, but instead a whare (house) of time. Here Te Reo Māori transcends the kōrero (talk); through geometric shapes and vibrant colour a narrative of resilience and strength of the Māori people emerges. The strokes and hues echo the stories and struggles of the local Māori when encountering colonial forces. An astute observer can discern stories of tribal connection and ancestral wisdom, paying homage to the ancestors who passed on this rich visual language. This art whispers to the viewer a future of resistance, preservation and reclamation of identity and heritage. The work challenges and confronts Aotearoa's colonial legacy that still shapes society, prompting reflection on the ongoing struggles for justice, equity, and cultural revitalisation. Quinton pays tribute to and endorses the revaluing of Te Reo Māori and suggests we are all in this together 'He waka eke noa'. It is apparent throughout his creative practice that Quinton is invested in the expectations of tangata whenua (people of the land) to pass on mātauranga (knowledge) is essential for generations to come.

Tai Timu Tai Pari has provided not only an opportunity for this group of artists and designers to create and present new research based in creative practice for a local audience, but to explore a wide range of denotative and connotative meaning associated with wai (water). Through the creative making process, our initial ideas changed, as we all resolved and grounded our practice in concepts of identity, people and place beyond the thematic context to engage in Te Ao Māori, Te Reo Māori, Māori values, Mātauranga Māori, Te Whare Tapa Whā (the 'house of four walls' metaphor for wellbeing) and principles of Te Tiriti o Waitangi. Their experience, skill and knowledge is authentic, tangible and relevant to the ākonga (students) with whom they work with as well as the wider public. This is an exhibition of and for changemakers, with the artists demonstrating to their audience their personal, educational and cultural investment in Te Ao Māori. They now respectfully pass on the baton for the future of Aotearoa New Zealand.

References

Tauranga City Council. (2022). *Te Rapunga Ora ki Te Papa City Centre Action and Investment Plan 2022 -2032*. Tauranga City Council. <https://www.tauranga.govt.nz/Portals/0/data/council/strategies/files/city-centre-action-investment-plan-aug2022.pdf>

Reese, A. (2018). *Te Papa: Naboth's Vineyard? Towards Reconciliation in Tauranga Moana: Executive Summary and Recommendations (Centre for Theology and Public Issues Series)*. (D. Tombs, Ed.). Retrieved from <http://hdl.handle.net/10523/8559>

tātou tāiao i runga i te tiorahanga a te ao Māori ki te whakakātau i te tauutuutu, te whakamāramaru kaha, te

Tohutoro

Tauranga City Council. (2022). *Te Kapunga Ora ki Te Papa City Centre Action and Investment Plan 2022-2032*. Tauranga City Council. [https://www.tauranga.govt.nz/Portals/0/data/council/stra/Tohutoro to te tiaki me te](https://www.tauranga.govt.nz/Portals/0/data/council/stra/Tohutoro%20to%20te%20tiaki%20centre-action-investment-plan-aug2022.pdf)

Reese, A. (2018). *Te Papa: Naboth's Vineyard? Towards Reconciliation in Tauranga Moana: Executive Summary and Recommendations (Centre for Theology and Public Issues Series)*. (D. Tombs, Ed.). Retrieved from <http://hdl.handle.net/10523/8559>

Ko te toi nei e muhumuhiu ana ki te kaimātaki he wā kei te heke mai mō te whakatepe, te tiaki me te whakakōra i te tuakiri me ngā taonga tuku iho. Ko ngā mahi e whakawero ana, e aro ana ki ngā taonga nei o te kōroni o Aotearoa e hanga tonu ana i te hāpori, e whai whakaro ana ki ngā pakanga e haere tonu ana mō te tika, me te whakaoaranga ahurea. Ka tuku mihia a Quinton ki te arotake i te reo Māori me te whakaro ki tātou katoa ki tēnei mahitahi. He waka eke noa' E kitea ana puta noa i ana mahi auaha, he mea nui a Quinton ki ngā tumanao a te tanagata whenua ki te tuku i te mātauranga mō ngā reanga kei te heke mai.

Ko Tai Timu, Tai Pari te whai wahi mō tēnei ropu kaitoi me ngā kaihoahoa ki te hanga me te whakakātau rangahau hou e pā ana ki ngā mahi auaha mō te hanga whakarongo o te rohe, engari ki te tūhura i te whānuitanga o ngā tikanga "denotative, connotative" e pā ana ki te wai. Nā roto i te mahi auaha, i huri o mātou whakaro tuatahi, i te mea ka whakakātauhia, ka whakakātauhia e mātou katoa ā mātou mahi ki ngā āria o te tuakiri, te tangata me te wahi ki tua atu i te kaupapa kia uru ki Te Ao Māori, Te Reo Māori, ngā uaratanga Māori, Mātauranga Māori, ka mutu Te Whare Tapa Whā me ngā mātapono o Te Tiriti o Waitangi. Ko o rātou wheako, o rātou pukenga me o rātou mohiotanga he pono, e kitea ana, e whai pānga ana ki ngā akonga e mahitahi ana rātou me te iwi whānui. He whakaaaturanga tēnei mō te hanga hurihuri, me ngā kaitoi e whakakātau ana ki te hanga whakarongo i ā rātou ake, mātauranga me o rātou tikanga ki te Ao Māori. Inaia nei ka tuku whakate

rātou i te toka mō te oranga o Aotearoa.

whakaaaro o te ohangā o te taonga tuku iho. Ko ngā tāpiri tuhiinga ka whakapaparitari i te kaimataki ki whakaaaro ki o rātou tūnga i te ao, me te pātai 'Me whakarekē te whakaaoro?', ki te kore he aha? Ko te mahi a Darcell 'Ka waiho e koe ngā tohu ki roto i ōku toto e waiho whakaaoro ana ki te pānga o te tāiao, ngā wāhi e nohia ana me te pūhea e taea ai e te tirohanga a te ao Māori me te tūrangā Eurocentric te mahitahi me tētahi. Ko te whakaaoro o te tuhiinga he whenua tātou katōa i te wā kotahi he wai, he wai e nuku ana ka waiho he pānga, he tohu, he tohu ki tētahi.

Ko ngā whakaaohua a **Dale Satter**, ko 'Flood', 'Teitei', 'Ebb' me te 'Low' ka hopu i ngā wāhanga e wāha o te neke tai, e whakamāramatia ana e ia hei whakaaata mō tana whanau tangata, tana haerenga, tana pōtiki me tō raua wā e haeretahi ana mai i Sulfur Point ki te papa tākaro o Strand Reserve. Ko ēnei haerenga e whakaaatu ana i ngā wheako kare-a-roto me ngā wheako o te piki me te heke. Ka rite ki te tai, ka timata tana tamaiti ki te hikaka me te kaha ki te kite i te taraka, te tereina, te aki aki, te pahi me ētahi atu meā ngāhau o te taiohi. Ka mutu ka hoki ki te hokinga ki te kainga, ngenge, me te pukuriri, me te hāhātia kia nohotahi me mānā me te pounamu wai reka. Ko te 'Tai Timu, Tai Parī' e pā ana ki ngā tumamakō a ngā mātua a Dale me te whanau tangata meake nei me tana tamaiti, ka pikitahi me ngā angitu me te ako mai i ngā rahunga. Ko ēnei whakaaohua e takaro ana me te tuhituhi; ko ngā huānga hoahoa kōrero pakīwaitara wehewehē i ahu mai i ngā kōrerorero me tana tamaiti i a ia e haere ana. Mōna, ko te ahua o te wāhi he mea huri noa; ko ngā hononga ki ngā wāhi ka haere mai, ka rere ano i te auhēke o te tai. Ka patapātai ia menā he ahua o te wāhi ngā ahuatanga o te wāhi, me pēhea te wai whakaaaro ki ngā taonga tuku iho o mua. Ka whakaaoro ia ki te tamāhā o te hitori o tō tātou whenua me te mea ka whakaaawe te tirohanga o nāianei mō ngā rā kei te heke mai, i te mea he mea nui te rekoata mō te whanau tangata i waenga i te pāpā me te tama i tēnei wā.

Ko te whakaurunga a **Nicol Sanders-O'Shea** e whakaaatu ana i te mahi tino uaua, he haerenga auaha he ahurei, he tukuru, he mutunga kore. Mōna, he rapu auaha mō te tikanga i roto i te wā o te huringa tonu. Ko ngā hoahoa kua anga ka whakatauiria i ngā ngaru e tuku ana i ngā atarangi ki runga i te pakitara

huri noa i ia mahi ka puta e ahua o te piki me te heke, te hohonu me te teitei. Ko te tukanga o te tā, te whiriwhiri i te taē, te hanga me te whakaurunga ki runga papatipu, ka whakanui i te huringa me tana ake wero o te manawanui me te pakari hei whaea, toī me te kaiwhakahāhare o te tangata. Ko ngā uaratanga Māori o te waiora, te taiora, te oranga me ngā manukura e kaha ana ki a ia; e pā ana ki te taiāo-ā-tinana, ki ngā tangata e tiakina ana e ia, ki te matauranga me te oranga o ia me ētahi atu, he mea nui ki te whakahihiri, ki te hanga, ki te poi poi i ngā hononga e mahitahi ana, e whakakotahi ana. Ka whakaaohua ngā mahi takitahi hei rōpu, he kupu whakarite pea mō te nohotahi i ngā wā hurihuri, me te hononga o te wai ki te tangata me te ahurea.

Ko **Anne-Marie Simon** te whakaaawe mai i ngā ahuatanga rerēke o te moana me ngā mea hanga o raro. Te kimi tikanga hohonu i roto i te aroha noa o te tiere, tō rārou tikanga herekore me te mana motuhake. Te hanga i ngā putanga miro mā te whakamahi i te huarangi auaha rerēke mā te whakamahi i te mihihi tuiwi whare me te papanga wetewete, ka ata mahi i ngā whakairo miro ahu-rotu hei whakairi ki te wāhi. Ka rite ki te ika i waho o te wai, ka tirohia ēnei mahi ki runga, kei tawhiti atu i te wai, kāore he hiahia ki te hoki mai. Ko ngā kaupapa matua Māori o te Tino Kāngatiratanga me te Mana Motuhake he inaki te tikanga e pā ana ki te kaha ki te noho i runga i te tino rangatiratanga, te mana motuhake me te mana whakahāhare. I roto i te whakaaoro ki ēnei arā, e whakaaatu ana te mahi a Anne-Marie ki a tātou e ahua mō te whakarekētanga ka ahua momotu mai i tō tātou taiāo o nāianei, engari ka kawea mai he koha ki tua atu i tā tātou e mohio ana ināianei. Ko ngā pae tawhiti, whāia kia tata. Ko ngā pae tāta, whakamaua kia tina. Ko te kaha mō apōpō ka whakawhirnaki ki tā tātou mahi i tēnei rā.

Ka awēhia a **Riley Claxton** e ngā mapi o te rau tau 1800 me te tuhi wai. Te tuhura i tēnei ahua o mua o te tuhi i te ahua o ngā ipu hei waka wai. Ko tētahi e whakaaatu ana i te ahua o te wāhi nei whakanui e whakaaohua o te wai me te wai tohutoro i roto i te hanganga me te hiranga o te oranga. Ko tētahi atu pātai menā he poma tālama tēnei mahi e tohu ana i te huringa o te poma. Ka hangaia he tikanga rau hei pātai menā he poma tālama tēnei mahi e tohu ana i te huringa o te rangi, he poma wai noa rānei hei

ngā uara me ngā tāonga tuku iho. Donna Dinsdale
nō Ngāti Pākehā, engari he hononga tona tane ki
Ngāti Marūkukere, he hāpu o Tapuika o te waka o Te
Arawa. E tautoko ana ia e tona whānau ki te hāpai i
ngā tikanga o Te Tiriti o Waitangi me te Mātāuranga
Māori mā te mahitahi, mā te kōrororero me te
whakawhitiwhitiwhakaaoro, ngā kawau me ngā tikanga
Ko te mārama me pēhea te whakaaoro, ngā ahuatanga
o te tirohanga a te ao Māori ki roto i te mahi i runga
i te whakautu kua noho hei wāhanga nui o tāna
rangāona, ko te ahua o te ahua, me te whakakōriki
mō te huringa, te whakahau, te tika me te nekehanga
i roto i te horopaki ahurea me te hitori o Aotearoa. He
whakaaro nui te mahi me te utaina o mua. Ko te wā i
mua i te tau 1838 me te haimātanga Tiriti he wā nui
i roto i tō tātou hitori, ā ka whiriwhiri a Donna ki te
tohu i ngā kākahu wahine o tēnei wā hei huarahi ki te
punga i te mahi i roto i te wā me te wāhi. Mā te tuhi
ki runga i tēnei horopaki o mua ka kōrero a Donna
ki te ahua o te kaha o te hāpori ki te hanga ahua me
te tuakiri. Ko āna mahi ka uru atu te kaimatātāki
ki te tirohira i ngā mahi o mua me o nāianei, mā te
whakamahi i ngā kākahu hei tirohanga e marama ai, e
taea ai te hanga ano i ngā hihiko o te hāpori.

I hūnuku mai a **Heidi Douglas** ki Aotearoa mai i
Kariwhāria i te tau 2004, i whiriwhiri ki te noho ki
te taha o Mauao hei wāhi mō te ao ki te whakaitipu
i āna tamariki. Ko tāna whakaahua e whakaatu
ana i te whakahohonutanga o te whānauatanga
me te whenua hei reanga tuatahi o te manene. I a
ia i te mea he tauwi, e whakaē ana ia ki te mahi
whakahēke whenua, me whakareke te whakaaro
kia uru ai ki tōna whenua whānau. Mā te whakamahi
i te arotahi hei taputapu whakaatu, ka tirohia e
Heidi tāna hononga ki tāna mauunga. Ko Mauao te
maunga, Te hopu i ngā kaupapa hurihanga i runga i
te maunga, ki te whakaatu i te ahua o te ao hurihanga,
te mahi whakaaoro, te whakangaaromānā, te mutunga,
hiringa o te whakamahi i te whenua. Ko te wāhi o tēnei
whakaaturanga e tū ana i runga i te auhēketanga o
ngā tai o te kōkoru. Ko tāua wai me te ora o te moana
ka haere mai, ka haere ki raro i ngā puranga, i rātou
e huri haere ana i Mauao me Te Moana ā-Toi katoa.
Ko enei whakaahua e tohu ana i tō tātou whenua,
me te ataahua, te aro me te whakautu e tika ana kia
kitea i roto i ngā hēnanga o Te Tiriti. Ko te raupapa
whakaahua a Heidi i ahu mai i ngā mātapono o te
Kaitiakitanga, te tiaki me te whakamāramaru o tō

tākaro? I roto i te raupapa whakaahua ka tirohira
ia ngā ahātanga rereke o te wai i roto i te rōhe o
Te Waiariki. Ka mau ana ahakāhaua i te rerekētanga
o ngā mahi Waiariki māori ki te noho taone, ngā
whakangāhau me ngā wāhi tūruhi motuhake ki
Rotorua/Waiariki e noho ana ia. Inā, ko 'Waiariki' te
kōrero mō ngā wai whakaora i tēnei takitwa. Ko te
waiere o Waiere kei te kairanga kua tanumia ki waho
atu o Rotorua i te huarahi ki Tarawera moana. Kei
reira te wai kākāriki mai i te roto o Rotokakahi, e
mohioitia ana e te tangata whenua ko 'Green Lake',
ka rere ki runga ki te roto o Tarawera. Ko te waiere
he whakamāmanahara ki te mā me te haerenga o te
wai hei mea e huri haere tonu ana, e neke haere tonu
ana. Nō tāna nei i whakaatuhia ai tēnei raupapa ki
Rotorua i tapaina ko 'Spend a night not a fortune' hei
papapātai i te pōhehe o te mahi tūruhi, engari i te wā
e whakaatu ana i āna mahi ano ki te Whare Uru, ko
enei whakaahua ka huri hei whakawhitiwhiti kōrero i
wēnganui i a Rotorua me Tauranga, mō te hitori o te
tauhokohoko i Te Waiariki.

Ko te whakamāoritanga o te 'Ko wai mātou', ko
'He wai mātou' me te 'ko wai mātou', na te mea ko
te wai te mea matua o te tuakiri me te oranga. Ka
torotoro a **Karolina Bemova** i ngā hanagarau hou
kia marama ake ai tona tuakiri. Ko tāna mahi i Toi
Ohomai Te Pūkenga he tautoko i te ako a ngā taurua
puta noa i te whānuitanga o ngā hanagarau matihiko
auaha, he rite tonu tāna whakanga o ki roto i āna ake
akoranaga i te mea he kaupapa mōna me ētahi atu.
Ka whakatewhatewha a Karolina i ngā tikanga mō
te tā #D me te tapahi tāhā e whakaatu ana i tona
tonutūnganga i te wā e maitoha ana ki ōna tūpuna me
ōna tūrangā ahurea e hanga ana i tona tuakiri. Ko te
kaupapa whakapāpai, he maumahara ki ngā taurua
puta noa i Uropi, he whakaitiingō 'nostalgic' ki a ia.
Ko ngā rangāhau auaha hou ki te tuakiritanga nā roto
i te hangarau ka taea te whakareke i o rātou pānga
ki te oranga o te ahurea. Ka whakaatu a Karolina i
tētahi angaanga kararehe kua whakarekētia me ngā
putanga hanga matihiko ki te pātai mena ka taea e
te hanagarau te pupuri pono i ngā pūkenaga me ngā
mātāuranga tuku iho mai i ngā tūpuna.

Ko te tuakiri me te ahua e kīia ana he hononga o roto,
ko te kākahu he whakapūakanga, he whakaaturanga
rānei o te tuakiri. Ka taea e te kākahu he kōrero tino
kitea me te kaha, ka taea te kawē kōrero mō te mana,

Tai Timu Tai Pari: Ngā kaitoi panonitia o ngā tai nukunuku me ngā tai nekeneke

ororongō me ngā urupare i waenga i ngā kaitoi
whakaatu. He kaha ngā nekehanga ki roto me te huri
noa i te wahi hou kua whakahoutia; ko te wao o Te
Āwanui kei te marino, kei te rongō kanohi, kei te kitea
te tangi o te ngaru kare e rangona.

Ko ngā ripene whakataa a **Kyle Sattler** mai i

ngā taputapu ngaru maru i mahia mai i te kata i
whakatātira ngā i te horopaki o tenei whakaaturanga
i roto i ngā kōrero hotaka o Tauranga Arts Festival.
I tangohia mai te kaupapa ngaru mai i te ripene

whakataa waiata pakīwātūhi mō te waiata 'Bing,
Bong, Dong' i hangaia e 'We Will Ride Fast' Nā roto
i te mahi raweke, i hangaia ngā raupapa pikitia neke
hei hanga i te kohinga 'ripple'. Ka whakaatuhia
hei whakaurunga ātaata-āroturuki maha mō te

maunahara i ngā ngaru māreparepa papatahi i te
taha o ngā matapihi e hono ana ki ngā ngaru o aho.
Ka whakaurua te oro ki roto i ia putanga kaupane

hei whakaohoo i te wheako o te tukutahitanga,
ina puta te ahuatanga oro me te ātaata i te wā kotahi
penei i te Motuhēhe me te Tukurua; Tauwahi me te
Wehenga; Tahī me te ehe; Te Mana me Te Tūtohu.

Roto i te whakaurunga o te papa a **Darcell Apelu**,
ko ngā puna o ngā tuhinga whakataa e tohu tika ana
i te ai hei huanga ki te huri me te noho tonu. Ki te
iwi Māori, ko te wai te mahi o te mauri me te mana.
Ko te pēhea me te wā e hiahia ana te ai e tapu ai,
mai i tō tātou whanautanga tae noa ki tō tātou mate.
Ka torotorohia Te Ao Māori, e mau ana i te oranga o
te tinana, te wairua, te whatumanawa, te nohotahi
me te taiāo. I roto i tana whakaro hou 'Death of
Prosperity' ka rere te wai ki raro i te rapapa o ngā
tūru maramara, e tohu ana i te whakapapa me te

Ko te tira o ngā kaitoi i roto i tenei whakakiteanga

he kaha te aronga toi whenuatanga me te wahi ki
Tauranga Moana, ki Te Waiariki whānui rānei. Ko
ētahi o rātou i whānau mai, i whakaitipua mai ki tenei
wahi o te motu, ko ētahi atu kua wahi huarahi ki te
rapu huarahi, ki ngā mea e taea ana me te whānau.
I waihangatia e mātou he kaupapa wahi o te wahi
whakaitūanga, ara ko te Whare Waka i te pito o

Taumata Kahawai. I whakaaehia a Tai Timu, Tai
Pari hei whakapūaki i ngā whakaro o te panoni, te
kotahitanga, te uka me te korikori i puta ai o rātou
whakaro auaha.

Kei te hitori o Tauranga ko te raupatu me te

whakataetāe mō te noho me te mana. Kua roa te
wā o Te Papa Tongarewa mō te houhanga rongō
ki te whakaora i te whakaae, ki te

whakaitūanga i ngā mahi o mua ki te wahi i ngā
mahia, mea ake nei e nohotahi ana, e hai hua ana,
e hakokotahi ana. E hangai ana te whakaaturanga ki
te tuhinga rautaki a te Kaunihera o Tauranga i te tau
2022, Te Rapunga Ora ki Te Papa, e whakaatu ana i te

māhere haumi me te tirohanga a te Kaunihera.

“...mana whenua restoring their mana

rangatiratanga over the city center, through
protecting, enhancing, commemorating and

celebrating those areas of significance to mana
whenua. In doing so, it also aims to enrich the
culture and identity for the wider community and

future generations to come”.

Mā te tangata takitahi, nā te mahi whakaro auaha i
whakaputa te whānuitanga o ngā whakautu ātaata,

Biographies

Darcell Apelu

Born and raised in Mount Maunganui of Niuean and Pākehā descent Darcell graduated with a Masters in Art and Design from Auckland University of Technology in 2013 and is now based in Tauranga. Since 2013, she's taught at Toi Ohomai Te Pūkenga in Poike. Darcell was a finalist in the Miles Art award held in Tauranga and also the John Fries Award in New South Wales. In 2019, Apelu was the Inaugural Recipient of the Lafaiki Residency in Niue and the Te Tuhi/Yorkshire Sculpture Park Residency in the UK. Notable exhibitions include the commissioned work *The Death of Prosperity 2020-2022*, at Te Tuhi Arts Centre and Tauranga Art Gallery and Ocean Memories at the Kunsthalle Fauste, Germany.

Quinton Bidois

(Ngāti Ranginui, Ngai Te Rangi) Que was born and raised in Arataki, Mount Maunganui. Que is a fluent talking Māori lecturer at Toi Ohomai Te Pūkenga and a practitioner in the art of Tā moko for more than 20 years.

Over the last two decades Que has established a reputation as one of Aotearoa's foremost Tā moko artists. He has a local and international practice and has been flown around the world to 'ink' his clients. Through Tā moko his designs connect individuals to their heritage and whakapapa.

Karolina Bemova

Tauranga based artist Karolina Bemova is originally from Slovakia. In 2018, Karolina finished her study at Toi Ohomai Institute of Technology and gained a Bachelor of Creative Industries degree. During her four years of study in creative industries, she has developed a broad creative skill set and expertise of conventional disciplinary approaches and digital media developments.

Riley Claxton

Riley Claxton's current position is Senior Arts Lecturer at Toi Ohomai Te Pūkenga. While he is primarily a photographer and graphic designer he also likes to paint and make things from clay. He has

a Masters of Fine Arts from Whitecliffe College of Art and Design. In 2015 he was awarded the Barfoot and Thompson Art Award held at Sanderson Galleries in Auckland as well as the Waiariki Institute of Technology Innovation in Art Award. He has work held in the Rotorua Museum collection.

Donna Dinsdale

Donna Dinsdale is an educator and practitioner specialising in fashion and the methodology of free-form sculptural drape. Her qualifications include a Diploma in Toi Maori Visual Arts (specialising in weaving), Bachelor of Design specialising in Fashion and a Masters of Art and Design (First class Honours) from AUT. She is currently employed as a Senior Academic Staff Member at Toi Ohomai Te Pūkenga in Tauranga, teaching on the Bachelor of Creative Industries. She has been a finalist three times in the WOW World of Wearable Art Awards with her 2022 entry 'Wahine Toa' highlighted in the Aotearoa section. She has won numerous art/design/fashion awards which include Westfield Style Pasifika New Zealand Fashion Awards, Overall Design of Excellence Award at Hokonui Fashion Design Awards and Molly Morpeth Canaday Art Award.

She draws upon her authentic cultural paradigms, with a nod to a strong systemic practice, the work encompasses traditional references while also allowing for the extension of fashion into the realms of self-expression: an alternate exploration, a cross-pollination of codes of attire, a cultural reverence and gender identity.

Heidi Douglas

Originally from California, Heidi Douglas moved to New Zealand in 2004, settling in Mount Maunganui in 2005. Over the years, her creative practice has incorporated photography, moving image, documentary, and curation. She is the recipient of the 2018 Alf Rendall Photography Scholarship and is a tutor of photography and graphic design at Toi Ohomai Te Pūkenga. She has a Master of Visual Arts first class honours from Auckland University of Technology.

Nicol Sanders-O'Shea

Nicol Sanders-O'Shea resides in Tauranga. She is a screen print specialist with a Master of Fine Art with first class honours from Elam School of Fine Arts, University of Auckland. Her current position is Academic Leader for Arts at Toi Ohomai Te Pūkenga. She has won several art awards including the prestigious WSA New Zealand Painting and Printmaking Award 2015. In 2018 she participated in a printmaking installation residency in New York. Her work has been selected for public gallery exhibitions in New Zealand. Her works are held in both public and private collections in New Zealand.

Dale Sattler

Residing in Tauranga, Dale is an educator, designer, illustrator, typographer, and coder. He has a mix of both local and international design industry experience.

His research interests lie in the intersection between design and notions of place. Dale's recent typeface works have explored responding to and translating local sites into typographic form. Many of these typefaces are available online.

He currently teaches graphic design on the Bachelor of Creative Industries degree at Toi Ohomai Te Pūkenga.

Kyle Sattler

Kyle Sattler is a multi-disciplinary artist, musician, and producer. He holds a Masters of Art (distinction) along with a Bachelor of Fine Art.

Sattler is currently employed as a visual arts tutor on the Bachelor of Creative Industries degree, at Toi Ohomai Te Pūkenga, in Tauranga. He teaches across a broad range of methodologies including, but not limited to: photography, drawing, painting, printmaking, installation art, sculpture, moving image, and sound art.

Sattler's current musical project, 'We Will Ride Fast', described as "what Robocop's band would be like if he was allowed to express feelings", blends a multitude of varying visual and sonic processes where the boundaries between the worlds of art and music are deliberately blurred. We Will Ride Fast released their 4th full-length studio album and second LP 'Army Of Invisible Zombies' in March 2023.

Anne-Marie Simon

Anne-Marie's journey has been a blend of fashion and education. Following her diploma in clothing and textiles, she dedicated two decades to diverse roles in the fashion industry. For the past 14 years, she has been teaching in tertiary education within the creative sector. Along this educational path, Anne-Marie gained a Bachelor of Design in fashion and a Master's in Educational Leadership with first-class honours. Beyond her academic and professional pursuits, she nurtures her artistic spirit by experimenting with machine and thread, crafting abstract portraits and sculptures. Currently holding the position of Principal Academic Staff Member, she teaches on the Certificate in Art and Design and the Bachelor of Creative Industries at Toi Ohomai Te Pūkenga.

Anne-Marie Simon

Ethereal Grace (Aroha Noa)

Drawing inspiration from the ever-changing nature of the ocean, this artist finds profound meaning in the ethereal grace of jellyfish, symbolising the perpetual ebb and flow of water. These mesmerising sea creatures, with their ability to radiate light in the depths of darkness, serve as a powerful metaphor for the interconnectedness of life.

Employing an unconventional approach, the artist utilises a domestic sewing machine on a dissolvable base, crafting 3D thread sculptures. Through this artistic endeavour, viewers are invited to immerse themselves in the captivating dance of nature's elements, offering a reflection on the timeless cycle of life, water, and human experiences.

This artwork serves as a conduit to contemplate the profound beauty and interconnectedness of our world, drawing parallels between the rhythmic movements of the ocean and the intricate journey of human existence.

Ethereal Grace (Aroha Noa)

3D thread, lights, dimensions variable, 2023

Dale Sattler

4 tidal movements.
4 panels of glass.
4 four cardinal directions.
4 fingers on corrugated iron.
4 legs, arms, eyes, ears.
4 typefaces.
4 slices of cheese.

Each illustration is a reflection of a section of the journey Dale's youngest son and he take, from Sulphur Point to the Strand Reserve playground. These journeys and this place emotionally reflect the rising and falling of the tides. With his boy excited to begin, excited to journey and hopefully see Taraka, Tereina, Aki Aki, Pahi, and all manner of other 2-year-old delights. To the journey home, tired, grumpy, wanting his Mummy and a little bottle.

Tai Timu Tai Pari speaks to Sattler as a parent, where his child is hopefully the best of him, rising with his successes and learning from his failures. Children are wrapped by their parents like the land is wrapped by the flood tide, and slowly as they age, they ebb the tide away, becoming their own. For his youngest, the tide is still in. For his oldest, the tide is halfway out. He already misses him.

'Flood', 'High', 'Ebb', & 'Low'
Digital prints, 1800 * 580mm, 2023.

PORO
AKI AKI
RIDE BIKE

Y
Z

MUSELI BAR
CRACKERS
CRACKERS
BUGG
OGG
KAI TIM
DON'T
SLOW
PLAY
JEMIA
BORO
AKI AKI
RIDE BIKE

HEAVY
DON'T
RIDE BIKE

TRAIN TRACKS

MIXED GROUND
NOVA LIGHT
OGG
ALL THE
DON'T
RIDE BIKE

OGG
DON'T
RIDE BIKE

WALK
DON'T
LOW
PUSH
SLIDE
OGG
KAI TIM
DON'T
LOW
PUSH
CROCK
OMA
SLIDE
MUSELI BAR
CRACKERS
CRACKERS
BUGG
OGG
KAI TIM
DON'T
SLOW
PLAY
JEMIA
BORO
AKI AKI
RIDE BIKE

Darcell Apelu
You Leave Traces In My Blood

'You Leave Traces In My Blood' considers a Maori World View of the environment in relation to the body. The 'body' is central to the thematic discourse of Apelu's practice whether it be a 'real' body of performative means, direct representation within a moving image or a placeholder signified in the form of a sculptural motif. Double-coding with the use of text and materials also informs this work and Apelu's wider practice.

Apelu's practice has previously engaged in perception of 'otherness' in an autobiographical sense; a direct invitation to 'exchange' of her own body and that of the audience. The audience is pivotal in these exchanges to move through a process of identification. Recent work still considers an exchange between the audience and the work, however, now with the use of monumental scale sculptural forms and text. The audience is invited to ponder their own position through the physical experience of the work and the text's statements. Such as of that of Sculpture of Death of Prosperity first commissioned at Te Tuhi Contemporary Art Trust 2020/21 a latter installation at the Tauranga Art Gallery 2021/22.

DOP text along the base of the functioning gilded fountain states: 'you will never possess the soil, you will never be secure' an inversion of a colonial quote by Edward Gibbson Wakefield 'Possess yourself of the soil and you will be secure'. This was Wakefield's catch cry to colonise Aotearoa. The double coded with meaning of Apelu's statement makes references to the trickle down effect of late capitalism, the impact of colonisation and the Maori world view that ownership of land is not seen through monetary means but a responsibility of kaitiakitanga, guardianship.

Subjective pronouns are used frequently by Apelu in the works she produces, such as 'You' in both Death of Prosperity and 'You leave traces in my blood'. Utilising 'you' within the text and title of this work is a direct challenge to the audience to foster some semblance of self-awareness positioning within cultural, social and economic systems, as did DOP. The artist hopes to create discourse of responsibility of the individual in relation to a larger group or communities it belongs to and holds space in.

More so the work alludes to whenua/land as a body, an entity that holds whakapapa. The formation of the work as a rigid snapshot of water is in reference to the environment. Wai/Water coerces Whenua to mold, it forms a scenario in which whenua is forced to respond and adapt. The same could be said for a 'being/body' that is adapting to the environment it inhabits. There are 'traces' left by the water that is absorbed by the land which in turn is transferred through whakapapa. The same way in which the environment impacts on experiences, identity and whakapapa. The 'traces' of experiences are held in the body and transcends to the next generations just as traces have been inherited from ancestors in bloodlines.

You Leave Traces In My Blood
Mirrored acrylic, dimensions variable, 2023.

1838

Donna Dinsdale

Located at the northern tip of Te Papa peninsula, the site of The Elms | Te Papa Tauranga known as Otamataha pā, is the landing place of ancestral waka and was home to a thriving Māori community.

In the early 1800's, local Māori chiefs understood the advantages a missionary presence could provide for trade and security. With their reputation as peacemakers, missionaries of the Church Missionary Society (CMS) were invited to live amongst Tauranga Māori and establish a mission station at Te Papa. Archdeacon Alfred Nesbitt Brown, and his wife Charlotte took up residence at Te Papa (Tauranga) in January 1838.

In all areas of his work, Alfred was supported by Charlotte Brown, who was described as pious and "superior in education to most female missionaries". Her teaching experience proved invaluable to her and she supervised the work at the station in the absence of her husband due to his frequent pastoral visits around the Bay of Plenty.

Research indicates that life at Te Papa was not easy for Charlotte who endured harsh living conditions and isolation from her home country. Her experience appears to have been complex, with both challenges and aspects of a rewarding nature. Despite these challenges, the comfort of some domestic normality would have given her a sense of routine and stability. Interaction with local Māori would have been a significant aspect of her experience. Missionaries often aimed to build strong bonds with local communities in which they served. These relationships could also provide a sense of purpose and fulfillment.

A deliberate reference to historical early 1800's women's clothing and accessories is used as a foundation to anchor this work in a specific time and place in reference to Charlotte Brown. By drawing upon this historical context, the audience

is invited to engage with the complex interplay between people, their attire, and the broader societal forces that shape fashion and cultural identity.

Class distinctions were often at the forefront of dressing during this period of time: this historical perspective underscores the social significance of clothing choices and how they were closely tied to one's place in society. Clothing also carried other social connotations, women more so than men, who, if dressed above or beneath their station were subject to societal judgements and perceptions. The state of cleanliness or dirtiness of clothing was another dimension through which individuals were evaluated.

The embedded reference of cross-cultural dressing through traditionally woven harakeke taonga and the materiality of discarded and aged textile resources which are overtly stained, disrupts these historical ideologies. This process of material and cognitive intervention brings to the forefront, the complex interactions and adaptations that occurred as a result of contact between Māori and European settlers.

1838 serves as a reflection of, and a catalyst for change, renewal, equity and movement within the cultural and historical context of Aotearoa. It engages viewers in a critical examination of the past and present, highlighting a deep connection to history and culture, using clothing as a lens through which to understand and potentially reshape social dynamics.

1838

Re-purposed painting canvas drop-cloth, harakeke, vintage New Zealand woollen blankets, 2023.

Photography;
Anne Shirley Fuse Media / design & photography.

Letters to the Maunga
Photographic print on Dibond

2023

This research project is an ongoing photographic representation of Douglas's deepening relationship with whenua as a first-generation immigrant. Identifying as tauiwi, or non-indigenous to Aotearoa New Zealand, Douglas acknowledges the decolonising process that must occur in her mindset to adapt to her adopted homeland.

Using the lens as a witnessing device, Douglas examines relationships between themselves and the maunga, Mauao, near where they live in Te Moana-a-Toi (the Bay of Plenty). This friendship, of sorts, between Douglas and Mauao has lent a familiarity and given her immense comfort. Mauao was a stable, omnipresent hoa as Douglas settled and raised a family in Aotearoa New Zealand.

Douglas searches for and photographically captures the events she recognises as changes on the maunga. These changes either result from colonial interference and long-term damage or are brought about through acts of reparation. Through photographic reportage and written letters, Douglas documents the changing relationship she has with the country she has adopted as an immigrant.

This project aims to honor Mauao for its friendship over the years by witnessing the process of repairing specific sites on the maunga. The letters and the photographic images represent significant beginnings towards taking care of and valuing the whenua of Aotearoa New Zealand. Douglas privileges the value of healing the past while looking to care for the future and honours the relationship which has grown between herself and the maunga; herself and her adopted homeland.

Heidi Douglas

Karolina Bemovo

Pozlátané tiene vlnenia Gilded shadows of the ripple

Karolina's artistic journey reflects a skilful blend of past and present elements, notably expressed through hand-carved animal skulls. This serves as a heartfelt tribute to her country of origin, blending continuity with transformation. Her time at Toi Ohomai has marked a significant step in her artistic growth. Reflecting on the impact of emigration, Karolina explored personal development. Weaving together past, cultural heritage, and present experiences in New Zealand, memories from

her homeland enriched her artistic exploration. The subtle rhythm of the tide mirrors changes in her collection. Carved skulls, inspired by her country's history, resonate with European patterns, reflecting global historical movements. Karolina emphasizes that technological change involves appreciating the past diversely, preserving and evolving cultural heritage through her dynamic artistic lens.

Poslátené tieňe vlnenia
Gilded shadows of the ripple
Bone, plywood, mdf, projection, 3D print, dimensions variable, 2023.

Nicol Sanders-O'Shea

Mediated images have become part of our daily routine and addiction. Daily we swipe through mass media content navigating images and information to seek and find meaning or entertainment. Sander-O'Shea's work explores the search (space and time) for meaning in a period of constant change. Te Awanui inspired this installation, the water being visually dominant in this exhibition. Water holds considerable significance to Māori, the frames stylistically mimic wave shapes, shadows fall on the wall around each work creating a sense of rising and falling. Together in change.

Multiple screen-printed imagery and patterns explore and employ creative strategies that disrupt and in contrast organise, this approach is used in product advertising and marketing, and historically a salon style presentation to entice the viewer/consumer. The printed imagery, random dots and patterns playfully unify the works. The process of printing, the choice of colour, the construction and the installation en masse overwhelmingly presents a celebration of change, a challenge of endurance and resilience. Waiora is a sense of wellbeing, physically, spiritually, emotionally, communally and environmentally, this is projected and reflected in Te Awanui. Connecting people and culture.

'Ebb and Flow'
Screen printed installation, 2023.

Quinton Bidois

"Colonial Narratives Unveiled: Deciphering korero muna within Te Reo Māori and Toi Māori"

In the heart of Tauranga, an art piece emerges as a poignant testament to the intricate tapestry of history, culture, and resistance that characterises the Māori experience in the wake of colonialism. As viewers engage with this artwork, they are invited to embark on a journey of discovery, where layers of meaning and symbolism reside, accessible to those who can read between the lines of Te Reo Māori and Toi Māori.

The perspex box is not merely a box but a whare of time, with strokes and hues that echo the stories and struggles of the local Maori in their encounter with colonial forces. At first glance, it may appear as an amalgamation of abstract shapes and vibrant colors, but as one delves deeper, a narrative emerges, one that speaks volumes to the resilience and strength of the Māori people.

Te Reo Māori, is woven seamlessly into the fabric of the artwork. Words and phrases are not mere elements of design but vessels of memory and protest. In this art, language transcends the spoken word, becoming a silent testament to the endurance of Māori culture despite the suppressive forces of colonialism. To those well-versed in Te Reo Māori, this art whispers the echoes of resistance, the preservation of heritage, and the reclamation of identity.

The Māori art tradition, with its rich symbolism and intricate patterns, provides another layer of interpretation. Within the art's geometric shapes and flowing forms, the astute

observer can discern stories of tribal connection, ancestral wisdom, and the enduring spirit of a people unwilling to be erased. These art pieces pays homage to the ancestors who passed down this visual language through generations, ensuring that the Māori narrative remains unbroken.

But this artwork is more than a reflection of the past; it is a call to action for the future. Just as the Māori have learned to read between the lines of history, so too must we acknowledge their resilience and indomitable spirit. This art challenges us to confront the colonial legacy that still shapes our society, prompting us to reflect on the ongoing struggles for justice, equity, and cultural revitalisation.

As we stand before these works, we are reminded that the ability to decipher its hidden messages is not just a skill but a responsibility. It beckons us to honor the Māori experience and support the revitalisation of Te Reo Māori, to ensure that the stories and wisdom contained within it continue to be passed on for generations to come.

"Colonial Narratives Unveiled: Deciphering Te Reo Māori and Toi Māori" is a testament to the power of art and language to transcend time and speak to the very essence of who we are. It is an invitation to join Māori in their journey of cultural reclamation and to acknowledge the profound significance of their history and heritage in the tapestry of Aotearoa New Zealand.

Colonial Narratives Unveiled: Deciphering korero muna within Te Reo Māori and Toi Māori
Perspex, acrylic paint, dimensions variable, 2023.

Riley

Flow 2023

In creating this painted work, Claxton was also interested in the flow state of water, specifically how water adopts any shape it is put into. In some ways, these works can be viewed as containers of water.

The expression Tai Timu Tai Pari also influenced Claxton's thoughts on the changing states of water. The way water flows through us is not only a part of us but also a requirement for life. According to (Mitchell et al., 1945), up to 60% of the human adult body is water, with the brain and heart composed of 73% water, the lungs containing about 83% water, the skin containing 64% water, muscles and kidneys at 79%, and even the bones being 31% water.

The work is designed to have a playful nature. While the image of a woman's profile celebrates the beauty of water, it also references the fact that water is a part of creation and sustains life on Earth. On the other hand, the image of the bomb pays homage to pop art and protest art, reminiscent of nuclear testing in the Pacific during the 1980s or the concept of a "weather bomb" that we are now becoming accustomed to due to the increasing effects of climate change. However, by filling the bomb with water, it diffuses the destructive nature of the bomb and transforms it into a water bomb, playing with words and turning it into an object of amusement.

Mitchell, H. H., Hamilton, T. S., Steggerda, F. R., & Bean, H. W. (1945). The Chemical Composition Of The Adult Human Body And Its Bearing On The Biochemistry Of Growth. *Journal of Biological Chemistry*, 158(3), 625-637.

Changing States 2023

Claxton

Changing states investigates water/wai as a motif one that is transmutable and hard to pin down. While the cargo shed is perched on top of the salt water of Tauranga Moana the photographs in changing states are of "fresh water" and are from Rotorua. Yet what Claxton is keen to highlight is that all water/wai flows to the sea and eventually that sea water itself becomes vapour and finds its way back into being rain and continues the cycle, from the mountain to the sea.

This continuing cycle of change, embedded in water/wai, one of the most precious elements we have on the planet, also highlights how precious life is and how thorough out our own lives we will also change, and to borrow from the theme of the show "Tai Timu Tai Pari" in life we also have to learn how to rise and fall with the tide.

This mahi which was all captured in Rotorua forms part of an ongoing series of work by Claxton called "Spend a night not a fortune. Since the middle of 19th century Rotorua's unique geothermal properties and enduring Māori culture have been presented in the form of paintings, photographs and postcards to lure in the domestic and international traveller. And while these images sit in parallel to tourist photographs or postcard images of Rotorua they aim to tell a different story, one that is less grand and sweeping, one where surreal qualities emerge, that blur the everyday with the strange, scratching beneath the surface and hinting at things that are strange, uncanny, timeless and unexplainable.

Water bomb
Acrylic on paper, 1500 * 1000mm, 2023.

Terrace diorama
Digital photo on archival photo rag, 420 * 594mm, 2023.